

Soil and crop management

Fertilizer nitrogen budget in rice fields

K. R. Reddy, Department of Biological and Agricultural Engineering, North Carolina State University, Raleigh, North Carolina 27607; and W. H. Patrick, Jr., Laboratory for Wetland Soils and Sediments, Center for Wetland Resources, Louisiana State University, Baton Rouge, Louisiana 70803, USA

To improve the efficiency of fertilizer nitrogen use by rice, it is important to know what happens to N applied to the soil. Fertilizer labeled with ^{15}N is used to distinguish fertilizer N from soil N.

A field experiment to determine the fate of applied fertilizer N was conducted on Crowley silt loam at the Rice Experiment Station, Crowley, Louisiana. Ammonium sulfate enriched with ^{15}N was applied at 100 kg N/ha by deep placement (7 cm in the soil by the side of each row, 10 cm apart) at the beginning of the growing season. Fertilizer ^{15}N was measured in the soil-plant system at harvest.

The fate of applied fertilizer nitrogen. Rice Experiment Station, Crowley, Louisiana, USA.

About a third of the added fertilizer N applied to the rice was recovered in the grain, about a fifth was recovered in the straw, about a fourth remained in the soil and roots, and the remaining fourth was unaccounted for and presumably lost from the soil system (see figure).

Split application of nitrogen in direct-seeded rice

R. S. Dixit and M. M. Singh, N. D. University of Agriculture and Technology, Faizabad, U.P., India

Nitrogen has become costly in India in the last few years. Its proper use is essential to maximize profits. To increase crop yields, not only is the quantity of

fertilizer important, but also the proper timing of its application. An experiment was designed through the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project to determine the best time of nitrogen application. The field trial was conducted during the 1974 and 1975 kharif seasons in the alluvial light soils of the Rice Research Station, Faizabad, where 1,260 and 1,248 mm of rain fell during

Grain yield of paddy under different nitrogen treatments, Faizabad, India.

Treatment	N application (kg/ha)	Amount of N applied (kg/ha) at			Paddy yield (t/ha)		
		Sowing	Tillering	Panicle initiation	1974	1975	Mean
T1	0	0	0	0	2.7	2.8	2.8
T2	60	60	0	0	3.5	3.9	3.7
T3	60	15	30	15	4.1	5.1	4.9
T4	60	20	20	20	4.6	4.9	4.8
T5	60	20	40	0	4.2	4.5	4.4
T6	60	0	20	40	3.9	3.9	3.9
T7	60	0	30	30	3.9	4.1	4.0
L.S.D. at 5%					0.54	0.58	

the two respective crop seasons.

Treatment T3 (15–30–15) produced the maximum grain yield (4.7 t/ha and 5.1 t/ha), followed by T4 (20–20–20) and T5 (20–40–0) during both cropping seasons. During 1974, treatment T3 produced significantly higher yields than T1, T2, T6, and T7, while during 1975, T3 gave significantly higher yields than T1, T2, T5, T6, and T7 (see table). When all nitrogen was applied at sowing, it was subject to loss through runoff, leaching, and weeds in upland, well-drained, light soils. However, a small quantity of nitrogen is essential to give the plants a good start after germination.

Efficiency of some phosphatic fertilizers with varying soil and water-management practices

U. C. Sharma, assistant soil scientist, Fruit Research Station, Udhoiywala, Jammu (JCK), India; and H. Sinha, head, Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, Ranchi Agricultural College, Ranchi-6, India

Studies on the efficiency of some phosphatic fertilizers in relation to soil and water management practices were conducted in the red loam soil (pH 6.3) of Kanhe Bihar, India. Phosphatic fertilizers were superphosphate, rock phosphate, yellow phosphorite, and ash-colored phosphorite. Liming and application of farmyard manure were the soil management practices under saturated, flooded-granulated, and flooded-puddled conditions. Among other data, the dry matter yield and the phosphorus content and its corresponding uptake were determined.

Dry-matter yield using superphosphate (44 g/plot) was significantly superior to that with rock phosphate (32 g/plot), ash-colored phosphate (30 g/plot), or yellow phosphorite (29 g/plot). The application of well-rotted farmyard manure significantly increased the dry-matter yield with the phosphates that were not water soluble, but had no effect with superphosphate. Lime significantly reduced yield with all phosphates. Flooded-puddled paddy gave 64.7% more dry-matter yield than flooded-granulated paddy, and 52.9%

more than saturated paddy. Flooding under puddled conditions was superior under all the soil-management practices. Under all water regimes, superphosphate was better than other phosphates. Farmyard manure gave better results in saturated conditions.

The phosphorus content due to superphosphate (0.103%) was significantly higher than that due to

rock phosphate (0.079%), yellow phosphorite (0.077%), and A.C. phosphorite (0.072%). Application of farmyard manure increased the phosphorus content, while various water regimes had no effect. Superphosphate application gave higher phosphorus content under all soil-management practices. Phosphorus uptake by paddy straw was significantly higher due to

superphosphate. The mean uptake was 44.6 mg/pot in superphosphate, followed by 27,23, and 23 mg/pot due to rock phosphate and yellow and ash-colored phosphorite. Lime application depressed the phosphorus uptake (20 mg/pot) and farmyard manure increased it (42 mg/pot). Flooded-puddled conditions increased phosphorus uptake.

Increasing rice yields under gall midge-infested conditions by increasing seedlings/hill

Weerawooth Katanyukul and Suchin Chantarasa-ard, Rice Entomology Branch, Entomology and Zoology Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand

Heavy gall midge infestation generally occurs during September and October in Northeast Thailand. The pest attacks only young rice buds and does not damage maturing rice plants. An experiment investigated whether rice yield under gall midge-infested conditions could be increased by increasing the number of rice seedlings. The experiment was designed in a split plot and replicated three times. Five rice varieties were studied: RD 9 and Meuy-Nong 62 M (resistant varieties), Kee-Tom-Laung (susceptible local variety), Dok-Ma-Li

105, and Niew-San-Pa-Tong (susceptible recommended varieties). Each variety was planted in a 6- × 12-sq-m-plot. The main plot was equally divided into three subplots where rice was transplanted at 3, 5, and 7 seedlings/hill. Gall midge-damaged tillers were observed at the peak of infestation (Sept. 14, 1976).

The percentage of damaged tillers did not significantly differ among hills with different numbers of seedlings (see table). In most cases, the average number of tillers and panicles significantly differed within each variety. Rice planted at 5 and 7 seedlings/hill produced more tillers and panicles than rice planted at 3 seedlings/hill. Overall mean rice yields did not differ significantly, probably because some varieties were resistant to gall midge and infestation on susceptible varieties was not heavy. However, the poor-tillering variety Kee-Tom-Laung

gave higher yields at 5 and 7 seedlings/hill than at 3 seedlings/hill.

Effect of root pruning and number of seedlings per hill on the growth performance of BR3 and Habiganj Boro VI in Bangladesh

Abdul Rashid Gomosta, senior scientific officer, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

During the boro season (Nov.—Apr.) in Bangladesh, farmers uproot seedlings by cutting the roots inside the soil or by pulling the seedlings without watering the seedbeds. To compensate for seedling mortality, the farmers transplant 5 or 6 seedlings/hill. This study was conducted to determine the effect of root pruning in relation to the number of seedlings per hill on the growth performance of BR3, a semidwarf rice, and of Habiganj Boro VI (HbjB VI), a traditional variety with long droopy leaves.

All seedlings recovered at the same time, whether or not their roots were pruned. Both the pruned and unpruned seedlings produced considerable roots. Pruned seedlings of HbjB VI produced more roots than the unpruned seedlings, but in BR3 unpruned seedlings produced more roots than the pruned seedlings. Root production per seedling decreased as the number of seedlings per hill increased. In both varieties, the relative tillering rate (RTR) decreased as seedlings per hill increased. The RTR value of HbjB VI dropped sharply as the number of days after transplanting increased, but that of BR3 changed less drastically during the early stage. The difference may indicate that the RTR value of a variety depends on its plant

Gall midge infestation, yield components, and grain yields of five rice varieties at different numbers of seedlings per hill at Phibun Mangsahan, Ubon Ratchatani, Thailand, 1976.

Treatment		Damaged tillers (%)	Tillers (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Grains (no./panicle)	Yield (t/ha)
Kee-Tom-Laung	3 seedlings	15.5	7.4	5.2	68	1.3
Kee-Tom-Laung	5 seedlings	10.6	8.5	5.8	81	1.6
Kee-Tom-Laung	7 seedlings	15.5	10.0	6.1	81	1.7
RD 9	3 seedlings	1.6	11.8	11.6	62	1.3
RD 9	5 seedlings	2.3	15.5	12.5	56	1.4
RD 9	7 seedlings	1.2	13.8	12.2	57	1.3
Meuy-Nong 62 M	3 seedlings	2.8	10.6	6.5	83	1.6
Meuy-Nong 62 M	5 seedlings	2.8	9.6	7.3	79	1.7
Meuy-Nong 62 M	7 seedlings	3.6	11.2	8.6	77	1.8
Dok-Ma-Li 105	3 seedlings	12.7	13.2	9.0	85	2.0
Dok-Ma-Li 105	5 seedlings	13.8	13.9	9.3	87	1.9
Dok-Ma-Li 105	7 seedlings	17.9	15.7	10.5	89	2.0
Niew-San-Pa-Tong	3 seedlings	13.5	7.4	6.0	102	1.6
Niew-San-Pa-Tong	5 seedlings	17.1	10.6	6.9	101	1.7
Niew-San-Pa-Tong	7 seedlings	13.1	11.8	7.5	102	1.8
LSD (5%)		n.s. ^a	1.79	0.58	n.s. ^a	n.s. ^a

^aNot significant.